

1 **APPENDIX**

2 **APPENDIX A.** Questionnaire Design

3 **Part I Respondent Personal Information**

4 Q1. Type of Your Organization [Single Choice] *

- 5 Construction Enterprise
- 6 Government Department
- 7 Design Institute
- 8 Consulting Firm
- 9 Real Estate
- 10 Other _____ *

11

12 Q2. Your Educational Background [Single Choice] *

- 13 Below College Level
- 14 College Diploma
- 15 Bachelor's Degree
- 16 Master's Degree
- 17 Doctorate

18

19 Q3. Your Professional Title/Position [Fill-in-the-blank] *

20 _____

21

22 Q4. Size of Your Organization [Single Choice] *

- 23 Under 50 employees
- 24 50-100 employees
- 25 101-200 employees
- 26 201-500 employees
- 27 501-1000 employees
- 28 1001-2000 employees
- 29 Over 2000 employees

30

31 Q5. Your work experience [Single-choice question] *

- 32 Less than 1 year
- 33 1-4 years
- 34 5-10 years
- 35 11-15 years
- 36 16-20 years
- 37 Over 20 years

38

39 **Part II: Case Collection**

40 Below are descriptions regarding the external environment, technology, organization, talent, data,
41 digital infrastructure and platform, collaborative cooperation, and strategy and top-level design of
42 construction enterprises undergoing (or having undergone) digital transformation, as well as the

43 outcomes of their digital transformation. Based on the descriptions below and the extent to which
44 they align with your understanding of actual conditions, please select an appropriate option for
45 evaluation.

46

47 **I. Environment (Hereinafter, “enterprise” refers to construction enterprises undergoing**
48 **digital transformation)**

49

50 Q6: The government has implemented policies and programs conducive to the enterprise's digital
51 transformation. Examples: Providing enterprises with necessary technical information support,
52 financial support, etc.

53

54 7 Strongly Agree, 6 Agree, 5 Somewhat Agree, 4 Neutral, 3 Somewhat Disagree, 2 Disagree, 1
55 Strongly Disagree

56 7 Strongly Agree

57 6 Agree

58 5 Somewhat Agree

59 4 Neutral

60 3 Somewhat Disagree

61 2 Disagree

62 1 Strongly Disagree

63 Q7: Diverse and rapidly fluctuating market demands have driven the enterprise to pursue digital
64 transformation

65

66 Q8: Pressure from clients and other stakeholders has prompted the enterprise to deepen its digital
67 transformation efforts

68

69 **II. Technology (Hereinafter, “enterprise” refers to construction enterprises undergoing**
70 **digital transformation)**

71 Q9: Enterprises utilize digital technologies such as BIM, IoT, big data analytics, and artificial
72 intelligence to optimize business processes.

73

74 Q10: In response to market and stakeholder demands, enterprises actively integrate technologies,
75 create digital services, enhance digital communications, and optimize business models.

76

77 **III. Organization (Hereinafter, “enterprise” refers to construction enterprises undergoing**
78 **digital transformation)**

79 Q11: To maintain competitiveness and adapt to digital transformation, enterprises undertake
80 significant organizational change or transformation and enhance corporate culture

81

82 Q12: Such enterprises feature flexible organizational structures and strong capabilities for business
83 process reengineering

84

85 **IV. Talent (Hereinafter, “enterprise” refers to construction enterprises undergoing digital**
86 **transformation)**

87 Q13: Enterprises prioritize hiring digital talent
88
89 Q14: Most employees possess high digital literacy (Note: Digital literacy refers to employees'
90 ability to utilize digital technologies in work practice).
91
92 Q15: Enterprises have standardized processes for cultivating digital talent and actively engage
93 with talent, e.g., establishing strategic agreements with universities to exchange knowledge and
94 attract interns and future talent to join the enterprise.
95
96 Q16: Digital talent constitutes a significant proportion of senior management.
97
98 **V. Data (Hereinafter, “enterprise” refers to construction enterprises undergoing digital**
99 **transformation)**
100 Q17: Enterprises utilize collected data for business operations such as product development and
101 learning, leveraging data to optimize decision-making.
102
103 Q18: Enterprises fully utilize data analysis to understand customer needs, actively communicate
104 with customers, and enhance customer satisfaction.
105
106 Q19: Data is one of the primary value-creating resources within the enterprise's business model.
107
108 **VI. Digital Infrastructure and Platform (Hereinafter, “enterprise” refers to construction**
109 **enterprises undergoing digital transformation)**
110 Q20: The enterprise prioritizes the acquisition and R&D of intelligent systems and equipment.
111
112 Q21: The enterprise actively advances the development of digital platforms for resource and
113 capability sharing, capacity matching, and production coordination to respond more swiftly to
114 market demands.
115
116 **VII. Collaborative Cooperation (Hereinafter, “enterprise” refers to construction enterprises**
117 **undergoing digital transformation)**
118 Q22: Enterprises actively establish partnerships with stakeholders to provide external input for
119 developing digital solutions and mutual learning from joint development, complementing
120 resources
121
122 Q23: Enterprises prioritize collaborations with universities, startups, and technology suppliers to
123 continuously foster open innovation practices
124
125 Q24: Enterprises adopt an open, proactive stance in exchanging ideas about digital technologies
126 and applications with employees, clients, and other partners.
127
128 **VIII. Strategy and Top-Level Design (Hereinafter, “enterprises” refer to construction**
129 **enterprises undergoing digital transformation)**
130 Q25: Enterprises actively pursue open innovation strategies to adapt to the current era of major

131 digital transformation and technological change.

132

133 Q26: Enterprises actively engage in strategic planning for digital transformation, formulating
134 guiding strategies and technical standards to refine concepts and enhance employees' value
135 recognition.

136

137 Q27: The enterprise fundamentally transforms its organizational design and strategic vision while
138 establishing new business objectives aimed at achieving more efficient operations to meet
139 customer needs.

140

141 **IX. Digital Transformation Outcomes (Hereinafter, “enterprises” refer to construction**
142 **enterprises undergoing digital transformation)**

143 Q28: The enterprise's digital transformation progresses smoothly, demonstrating vigorous
144 momentum.

145

146 Q29: Overall management efficiency significantly improves post-digital transformation, with
147 enhanced customer relationship maintenance.

148 Q30: Post-digital transformation, the enterprise experiences notable increases in profits, assets,
149 overall operational efficiency, sales revenue, market share, and overall corporate reputation.

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